

Speckle Reduction Through Angular Compounding in Robotically Assisted MHz-OCT

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Abstract: We demonstrate speckle reduction in robotically assisted MHz-OCT by angular compounding. The robot is used to acquire images from different angles, which, after registration, are used for efficient speckle averaging without loss of spatial resolution. © 2025 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

Optical coherence tomography (OCT) is a high-resolution imaging modality widely used in clinical diagnostics. As a coherent imaging technique, it suffers from speckle noise, which degrades image quality. Speckled images exhibit a granular appearance composed of dark and bright spots that do not correspond to actual structures in the sample. Instead, they result from the interference of backscattered waves reaching the detector out of phase within the coherence time of the light source [1]. As a form of high-contrast noise, speckles make it difficult or even impossible to distinguish fine structures, requiring methods of speckle reduction.

A potential approach to obtain a speckle-reduced image is to create a composite image from multiple images with uncorrelated speckle patterns [1]. Spatial compounding accomplishes this by averaging images corresponding to adjacent regions. However, the inherent spatial misalignment of this method leads to a loss of resolution and introduces blurring in the resulting image. An alternative method is angular compounding, where a composite image is derived from images that contain the same spatial information but decorrelated speckles. This technique relies on modulating speckle patterns by altering the phase difference between scatterers, which is achieved by changing the incident angle of the illumination [2]. The voxel intensities in images acquired from different viewpoints are modulated by an angle-dependent phase shift and averaged to create a more uniform distribution.

Commonly, angularly diverse images are acquired by shifting a collimated incident beam off the optical axis of the objective lens to alter the incident angle [2]. In contrast, we employed a robotic system for image acquisition, as it provides maximum flexibility in selecting the axis of rotation and enables the capture of images at significantly larger angles. After image acquisition and before averaging, proven methods of intensity-based image registration have been used to find corresponding points between images captured from different viewpoints, as they are displaced relative to each other.

In this work, we present speckle-reduced images as preliminary results of robotically assisted angular compounding.

2. Material and Methods

The combination of MHz-OCT and an articulated robot is an approach for large-area imaging and has been implemented as Large Area Robotically Assisted (LARA)-OCT [3]. An overview of the setup is provided as Fig. 1. It consists of a MHz-OCT system with its scan unit mounted to the flange of the manipulator which is part of a robotic system composed of an articulated robot and its controller. A workstation serves as a link between the systems via various LabVIEW applications, enabling fully automated imaging sequences.

The positioning component is formed by the LBR iiwa 14 R820 (KUKA AG, Germany), a 7-axis articulated robot. The imaging component is a home-built OCT system based on a 3.2 MHz Fourier Domain Mode Locked (FDML) laser [4] operated with a spectral bandwidth of 100 nm and a central wavelength of 1310 nm. As a measure of lateral resolution, the waist of a diffraction-limited beam at the central wavelength can be specified as 29.8 μm with a theoretical beam divergence of 3.2°. For axial resolution, an approximate value of 15.1 μm can be given, based on the spectral bandwidth and central wavelength. The power on the sample is approximately 25 mW. The scan unit contains two galvanometer scanners (dynAXIS 421, Scanlab GmbH, Germany) and imaging optics in a telecentric configuration for volumetric imaging.

While the method is primarily intended for applications in dermatology, where the robot is used to ensure a controlled, consistently orthogonal orientation and constant distance to the surface when gradually scanning large areas, the robot's high degree of freedom can also be utilized in angular compounding to capture images under defined orientations. In contrast to the progressive shifting of the optical focus, control of orientation and distance to the surface with alternating image acquisition in large-area OCT, angular image acquisition implements an automated

interplay between image acquisition and modulation of the viewpoint, while the focus position remains largely unchanged.

With a fixed focus position, a spherical image acquisition scheme emerges, where each viewpoint - under which an angular image is captured - can be defined as a position on the surface of a sphere. The radius of this sphere is arbitrary but can be set intuitively as the focal length of the scan lens, as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: LARA-OCT-System. A combination of MHz-OCT and an articulated robot for large area image acquisition.

The simplest form of spherical image acquisition involves rotation around one axis and produces angular images from viewpoints along great circles of the sphere, as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Great circle image acquisition. Successive rotations that produce movement and viewpoints along an orthodrome of the imaging sphere.

As seen in Fig. 2, the images captured during spherical image acquisition are rotated relative to each other, requiring alignment before averaging. The open-source software elastix [5,6] provides well-established methods for intensity-based image registration and has been used to determine both rigid and non-rigid transformations between angular images. Within this approach, the image captured from the viewpoint without rotation has been considered the reference image, while all other images are treated as moving images.

A composite image was constructed as an arithmetic average of the registered moving images.

3. Results and Discussion

A selection of preliminary results of robotically assisted angular compounding using great circle image acquisition are shown in Fig. 3. The composite image of the proximal fingernail fold and part of the nail (Fig. 3B) was constructed as an arithmetic average of 8 angular images, captured at angles $\pm 2^\circ$, $\pm 1.5^\circ$, $\pm 1^\circ$, $\pm 0.5^\circ$, with dimensions of $1500 \times 1500 \times 600$ voxels. These images were registered, resampled, and averaged within the domain of the reference image captured at 0° (Fig. 3A). The same method was applied to 4 angular images of a fingertip, captured at angles 1° , 2° , 4° , 5° , with dimensions of $1000 \times 1000 \times 600$ voxels. This process resulted in the composite image shown in Fig. 3D, resembling the reference image at 0° (Fig. 3C). The reduction in speckle contrast increases the ability to distinguish finer structures and tissue layer boundaries in both composite images. The absence of noticeable blurring suggests that the resolution has been preserved, and that image registration has introduced only minimal spatial compounding.

Fig. 3: Comparisons between reference images and composite images. Left: The composite image (B) of a proximal fingernail fold displays distinguishable layers and reveals finer structures than the reference image (A). Right: The composite image (D) of a fingertip shows sharper lines and a more recognizable sweat gland compared to the reference image (C).

4. Conclusion and Outlook

We demonstrate that angular compounding using robotically assisted MHz-OCT produces speckle-reduced images with visibly enhanced image quality. Since this study only qualitatively examined speckle reduction, future research should include a quantitative assessment using appropriate metrics. Such an analysis would help investigate the relationship between speckle reduction in composite images and the range of viewpoints they are based on. Naturally, future work must also incorporate more complex spherical imaging patterns to maximize the solid angle of acquisition. Furthermore, examining changes in resolution will help determine how much spatial compounding is introduced in image registration and whether there are even possibilities for resolution enhancement given sufficient accuracy of alignment.

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